

ISic0815

Epitaph of Zoe

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Cozzo Cicirello

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Super lo
2. cellum, u
3. bi iaceo e
4. go virgo
5. nomi
6. ne Zoe
7. annorum
8. quinquaginta
9. menses VI
10. adiura
11. te per de
12. um et infero
13. s: nemi
14. ni lice
15. at aperir [e]
16. cupa
17. m

Apparatus

standardised text taken from Korhonen 2010: 132-3

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175813

EDR 074418

EDCS 12800326

Bibliography

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